

Supplementary Information

Cross-linkable polymer-based multi-layers for protecting electrochemical glucose biosensors against uric acid, ascorbic acid and biofouling interferences

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Materials and methods

Figure S1: Chemical structures for the negatively charged polymers tested. Monomer ratio in P(SS-GMA-BA) is SSNa:GMA:BA 5:3:2 while ratio in P(VI¹²-SSNa¹) is x = 12, y = 1 and ratio in P(VI¹-SSNa¹) is x = 1, y = 1.

Figure S2. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (200 MHz, D_2O) spectrum of the P(SSNa-GMA-BA) polymer

Figure S3. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (200 MHz, D_2O) spectrum of the P(SSNa¹-VI¹²) polymer

Figure S4. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (200 MHz, D_2O) spectrum of the $\text{P}(\text{SSNa}^1\text{-VI}^1)$ polymer

Supplementary results

Figure S5: Amperometry at 350 mV for the system coated with P(SSNa⁵-GMA³-BA²) (green), P(VI¹²-SSNa¹) (red) and P(VI¹-SSNa¹) (blue) in PBS (0.05 M, pH 7.4).

Figure S6: Amperometry at 350 mV for the uncoated control Case I in PBS (0.05 M, pH 7.4) and PBS containing uric acid at physiological concentration.

Table S1. K_M^{app} and j_{max} for uncoated control Case 1, and systems coated with MPC Case II and Nafion Case III in PBS and artificial plasma. (n = 3, Mean \pm SD)

Media	Non-coated control		MPC		Nafion	
	K_M^{app} / mM	j_{max} / $\mu A cm^{-2}$	K_M^{app} / mM	j_{max} / $\mu A cm^{-2}$	K_M^{app} / mM	j_{max} / $\mu A cm^{-2}$
PBS	26.2 \pm 1.1	557 \pm 11	13.7 \pm 3.1	455 \pm 13	23.4 \pm 4.7	261 \pm 13
Artificial Plasma	23.0 \pm 1.4	394 \pm 8	15.5 \pm 0.1	427 \pm 13	81 \pm 10	218 \pm 11

BSA	7.3 ± 1.2	292 ± 8	14.6 ± 4.8	486 ± 20	69.8 ± 5.1	278 ± 8
Uric Acid	14.3 ± 4.5	285 ± 14	10.9 ± 1.2	249 ± 2	20.1 ± 3.2	296 ± 11

Figure S7: Amperometry at 350 mV for the uncoated control Case I (dark red), MPC Case II (green), P(VI¹-SSNa¹) Case IV (yellow), enzyme layer Case V (violet) and novel polymer design Case VII (pink) in PBS (0.05 M, pH 7.4) with injections of A) uric acid and B) ascorbic acid.

Figure S8: Expanded view of figure S7 amperometric response at 350 mV for the uncoated control Case I (dark red), MPC Case II (green), P(VI¹-SSNa¹) Case IV

(yellow), enzyme layer Case V (violet) and novel polymer design Case VII (pink) in PBS (0.05 M, pH 7.4) with injections 5 mM glucose.